

A methodological approach to assess the impact of a motorway on visual landscape.

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The introduction of new large structures such as a motorway represents a visual intrusion that may reduce visual quality (determined mainly on the bases of three groups of factors: geomorphology, vegetation, and land use). This reduction or “visual impact” is related, on the one hand to the degree of visibility of the new structure (magnitude) and, on the other hand, to the contrast between the structure and pre-existing landscape (intensity).

The analysis of visual impact has been based on the identification of integrated environmental units defined on the basis of geomorphology, land cover and human occupation. The intrinsic visual quality of those units has been determined according to categories of visual quality defined for geomorphology and land use-cover units, separately. To obtain the visual quality of units, values of landform and land use-cover were combined by a matrix. Motorway sectors were defined by overlapping motorway alternatives over the map of visual quality previously obtained. These sectors were used to measure the magnitude of impacts.

The analysis of the visibility of the new structure was based on the identification of significant viewing points in the motorway sectors described above. The visibility has been expressed as “area from which the structure would be visible” and “population or potential viewers of the new structure”. A single value was obtained for motorway sectors

identified (corresponding to integrated landscape units) by averaging the values for all points contained in each sector. The values obtained correspond to “total area from which some point of the new motorway would be visible” and “average viewing area and population for any sector of the motorway”. A combined expression of the area from which a point or sector is visible and the number of viewers is provided by the product between both values and it was used as a measure of the magnitude of impacts.

Intensity has been considered to be directly related to the visual quality of units affected and it was expressed as a correction factor to be applied to the magnitude value obtained, in order to have an integrated assessment of visual impact including both magnitude and intensity.

Geomorphologic performance was obtained using the size ratio between the new landform created and the size of natural and the size of the new structure has been expressed as area of the average vertical section and compared with relevant natural linear landforms, be it positive or negative. It is not unreasonable to assume that the lower those values the more “sustainable” the new project would be from the point of view of preserving the visual heritage of the area.

Relevance of impacts was established by comparison with well-known examples of visual landmarks in the region, especially cases which might have been subject to specific visual enhancement actions. This could help to determine the social importance of the impact and the expense local society would be willing to accept its mitigation. For the assessment of relevance, two large buildings were analysed in the main towns in the study area and compared with new structure.

Mitigation measures have been proposed. They should include visual barriers to reduce visibility and contrast between the new structure and the environment; this can be achieved through choice of materials, design details, paint and vegetation.

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Introduction

A motorway represents a visual intrusion that may reduce visual quality. This reduction or "visual impact" is related to the degree of visibility of the structure (magnitude) and to the contrast between the structure and pre-existing landscape (intensity). Visual impact assessment has been carried out by analyzing and Integrating both magnitude and intensity. The visual quality (intrinsic merit of a unit from a perceptual point of view) and fragility (sensitivity to visual intrusion from human activities) of landscape is determined mainly by three groups of factors: **geomorphology** (relief, shape, rock type); **vegetation** and **land use** (especially presence of impacting elements such as prominent constructions). The method has been applied to a new motorway between Vitoria and Elbar in the Basque Country, Spain. Key issues in the assessment process are briefly discussed.

Geomorphologic performance:

Criteria applied are ratio between the size of the new landform created and the size of natural, linear landforms in the area. Percent of the study area from which the new structure will be seen can also be used. It is not unreasonable to assume that the lower those values the more "sustainable" the new project would be from the point of view of preserving the visual heritage of the area.

Relevance of impacts:

If it is established by comparison with well-known examples of visual landmarks in the region, this could help to determine the social importance of the impact and the expense local society would be willing to accept to mitigate it.

Data needs:

DEM; map of integrated environmental units; geomorphological map; land cover-use map; roads and built-up areas; population data; relevant visual landmarks as standards for comparison.

Operating procedure

The analysis of visual impact has been based on the identification of integrated environmental units defined on the basis of geomorphologic, land cover and human occupation (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Integrated landscape units

The intrinsic visual quality of those units has been determined according to the following procedure and criteria:

1) Ranks of visual quality were established for the two components considered in the former units (Tables 1a, 1b).

2) Landform and land cover were combined to define visual quality as shown in Table 2.

Table 1a. Categories of visual quality for land use-cover units.

ID	Land use-cover unit	Visual quality
01	Urban areas	1
04	Industrial	1
06	Cultivated prairie and crops with hedgerow	2
10	Terraced crops and cultivated prairie	2
13	Shrubs	4
18	Rock	4
19	Alfalfa pastures	3
20	Deciduous forests	5
23	Crops / alfalfa pastures mosaic	3
24	Crops / forest mosaic	4
25	Forests / alfalfa pastures mosaic	4
26	Mixed forests / shrubs mosaic	5

Table 1b. Categories of visual quality for landform units.

ID	Landform unit	Visual quality
01	Alluvial plain	1
03	Valley floor and adjacent slope	2
10	Valley slopes and gentle interfluvies	3
11	Abrupt summits and crests	4
12	Network of small valleys and interfluvies	5

Table 2. Matrix of visual quality values obtained by the combination of landform (M) and land cover-use (V-H) values.

V-H	M	1	2	3	4	5
1	1	1	1	2	3	3
2	1	1	2	2	3	3
3	1	2	2	3	3	4
4	1	2	3	3	4	3
5	1	3	3	4	4	3

Fig. 2. Overlap of motorway alternatives and visual quality units.

3) Motorway sectors were defined overlapping motorway alternatives and visual quality map (Figure 2). These sectors were used to measure the magnitude of impacts.

Final comments

The results obtained show that the combined average visibility of any motorway sector is considerably lower than the reference value (standard) in the case of alternative A, but more than twice as great for alternative B. That is, this alternative would imply the introduction of an artificial structure much more intrusive from the visual point of view than existing structures in the study area, if the quality corrected values (Impacts) are considered, visual intrusion would be lower, equivalent to about half the combined visibility of the reference structure for alternative B and less than 5% for alternative A. Mitigation measures to reduce visual impact should include visual barriers to reduce visibility (vegetation, "naturalised" earth accumulations, etc) and contrast between the new structure (landforms, shapes, colours, textures) and the environment. Compensation through the elimination of "eyesores" in the area (derelict land or structures, spoil heaps, etc) during the period of construction is another possibility. The method described allows the assessment of impacts using units with specific, measurable magnitudes, thus ensuring replicability of results and reducing subjectivity.

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Visibility analysis

Significant viewing points in the motorway sectors were used to determine visibility. Visibility was expressed as "area from which the structure would be visible" and "population or potential viewers of the new structure". A single value was obtained for motorway sectors identified by averaging the values for all points contained in each sector. Visibility thus obtained should therefore be interpreted as "maximum visibility". Figures 3a, 3b and Table 3 represent visibility for the two alternatives analysed.

Fig. 3. Visibility of motorway: a) alternative A; b) alternative B.

Table 3. Visibility of motorway alternatives

		A	B
VISIBILITY AREA km ²	Total	41,29	62,29
	Section sum*	100,43	322,46
	Section average	8,37	26,87
VIEWING POPULATION pop.	Total	2,736	4,124
	Section sum*	3,287	14,951
	Section average	318	1,245
COMBINED VISIBILITY km ² * pop	Total	112,968	309,343
	Section average	2,681	33,453

* Sum of visibility areas or viewing population for all motorway sectors, regardless of overlap.

A combined expression of the area from which a point or sector is visible and the number of viewers is provided by the product between both values, (Table 3).

Impact assessment

Visibility area/population are used as a measure of the magnitude of impacts. Intensity was directly related to the visual quality of units affected and it was expressed as a correction factor (Figure 4) to be applied to the magnitude value obtained, in order to have an integrated assessment of visual impact including both magnitude and intensity. Table 4 shows impact values obtained using this procedure; Alternative B clearly has the greatest visual impact.

Fig. 4. Relationship between visual quality of units and correction factor applied to magnitude values.

	A	B	
VISIBILITY AREA km ²	Quality-corrected section sum	45,24	172,94
	Quality-corrected section average	3,77	14,41
	Quality-corrected section sum	1,692	7,452
COMBINED IMPACT (km ² * pop)	Sum	76,548	1,388,749
	Section average	532	8,949

Table 4. Visual impact of motorway alternatives.

To assess geomorphologic performance the size of the new structure has been expressed the ratio between average vertical sections (AVS, product between length and average height) of motorway and relevant natural linear landforms, be it positive (ridges, crests) or negative (valleys, gorges). The Deva valley (V) itself and a pronounced crest (C) have been used as standards. The values obtained were:

$$R_s (A)_V = AVS_A / AVS_V = 84,250 / 304,000 = 0,28;$$

$$R_s (A)_C = AVS_A / AVS_C = 84,250 / 150,756 = 0,55;$$

$$R_s (B)_V = AVS_B / AVS_V = 454,608 / 304,000 = 1,5;$$

$$R_s (B)_C = AVS_B / AVS_C = 454,608 / 150,756 = 3$$

Landform modification could thus be considered as acceptable in the case of alternative A, but not for alternative B.

An assessment of relevance has been made by comparison with the visibility of two large structures (buildings) in the area (Figure 5). Visibility of both points is quite similar, the average has been used for comparison (Table 5).

Visibility ratios (Rv) were obtained for those visual landmarks, using both "average sector visibility area", and "average sector viewing population". Area visibility of the reference points considered (point 1) is similar to average area visibility of sectors in the case of alternative A. Population visibility of this alternative is much lower. Alternative B has much higher area visibility than the reference point, and slightly lower population visibility.

Table 5. Visibility of structures used for comparison

Visibility point	Area (km ²)	Population (persons)	Combined visibility (km ² * persons)
1 (Elbar)	8,34	1,898	15,829
2 (Vergara)	10,4	1,419	14,756
Average 1 + 2	9,37	1,659	15,294

A synoptic comparison is provided by combined area x population values. Visibility ratios (Rv) have been obtained.

$$R_v = \frac{\text{Combined impact motorway alternative}}{\text{Average combined visibility standards}}$$

$$R_{vA} = 532 / 15,295 = 0,03;$$

$$R_{vB} = 8,949 / 15,294 = 0,59;$$

Thus alternative B represents a more significant departure from existing conditions than alternative A.

Figure 5. Visual landscape: reference points.